

Hanging arm in the non-operative treatment of proximal humerus fractures

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The classic rehab protocol in the non-operative treatment of proximal humerus fractures includes 2-3 weeks of shoulder rest in a sling followed by pendulum exercises.

The shoulder rest period may induce shoulder joint stiffness and increased motion at the fracture site when starting pendulum exercises, which may increase the risk of non-union or malunion.

The hanging arm protocol consists in encouraging the patient since day one to lean forward very slowly trying to reach the toes with the finger tips and again very slowly getting up, as long as the procedure is completely painless.

The hanging arm protocol aims at keeping a totally mobile shoulder joint using only gravity in order to avoid motion at the fracture site, which may lower non-healing risk and may increase the functional outcome.

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